

Vitiligo-Like Secondary to Ribociclib: A Case Report

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ABSTRACT

Ribociclib, a cyclin-dependent kinase (CDK) 4/6 inhibitor, is widely used in the treatment of metastatic breast cancer. However, its dermatologic adverse effects, particularly vitiligo-like lesions, have been recently reported. The pathomechanisms underlying these lesions remain unclear, but immune-mediated melanocyte destruction has been proposed. A literature review reveals an increasing number of similar cases, highlighting the need for further investigation into these adverse effects' incidence, mechanisms, and clinical implications. We present a case of vitiligo-like depigmentation in a patient undergoing ribociclib therapy.

KEYWORDS: vitiligo, ribociclib, case report, dermatologic toxicity, adverse effects

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I. INTRODUCTION

Ribociclib is a selective CDK4/6 inhibitor approved for use in hormone receptor-positive, HER2-negative metastatic breast cancer. Its efficacy has been well-documented, but dermatologic toxicities, including vitiligo-like lesions, have emerged as an unexpected adverse event (1,2). Reports indicate a growing number of cases describing extensive depigmentation associated with ribociclib use (3-5). While the precise pathogenesis remains under investigation, immune-related mechanisms, including the activation of T-cell-mediated melanocyte destruction, have been suggested (6,7). This case report contributes to the growing literature on ribociclib-induced dermatologic toxicities.

II. CASE PRESENTATION

A 62-year-old woman with metastatic breast cancer was initiated on ribociclib in combination with letrozole. After five months of therapy, she developed well-demarcated, non-scaly depigmented patches on her upper and lower

Extremities. The lesions progressively increase, resembling vitiligo (figure 1). Wood lamp examination demonstrates increased sharpness of border lesions and fluoresce bright blue-white, showing decreased or absent intervening melanin (figure 1). Dermoscopic examination revealed depigmentation and erythematous areas (figure 1). A skin biopsy showed positive Masson-fontana staining in melanophages of the superficial dermis, it confirmed the absence of melanin in the basal layer of the epithelium (vitiligoid lesion) (figure 2). She had no personal or family history of autoimmune conditions or previous skin disease. She does not refer systemic symptoms accompanying the dermatologic changes. The patient showed adequate efficacy with treatment with ribociclib, so the oncology service decided to continue with the therapy. Regarding vitiligo-like, we decided expectant management, due to the poor response to treatment. Follow-up, the depigmentation lesion remained stable over the subsequent six months of treatment.

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Figure 1. (A) Depigmented macules over the forearms. (B) Wood lamp examination lesions demonstrate increased sharpness of borders and fluoresce bright blue-white. (C) Dermoscopic image of depigmented macules and erythematous areas.

Figure 2. (A) Mild interface dermatitis, with moderate chronic perivascular infiltrate; melanophages are also observed in the papillary dermis. (Haematoxylin and eosin, 4x). (B) Moderate chronic inflammatory infiltrate in the skin adnexa (perifolliculitis), and melanophages in the papillary dermis (Haematoxylin and eosin, 10x). (C) Detail of melanophages in the superficial dermis, and mild chronic perivascular infiltrate. (Haematoxylin and eosin, 20x). (D) Positive staining is observed in melanophages of the papillary dermis and the epithelium's basal layer. (Masson-fontana staining, 10x). (E) Positive staining in melanophages of the superficial dermis; absence of melanin is observed in the basal layer of the epithelium (vitiligoid lesion). (Masson-fontana staining, 20x).

III. DISCUSSION

There are around twenty-five reported cases of patients with ribociclib who present depigmenting lesions (3). A

review of published cases indicates that these lesions typically appear within the first year of treatment (3-5). The mechanism by which ribociclib induces these lesions

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remains unclear, but immune-mediated melanocyte destruction is a likely explanation (6,7). CDK4/6 inhibitors can alter immune responses, leading to increased T-cell activity against melanocytes, a process similar to the pathogenesis of idiopathic vitiligo (8,9).

Dermatological toxicity accounts for 15% of all reported adverse events (5). The most common dermatological adverse effects are alopecia in 15-30%, stomatitis in 10-30%, rash in 11-19%, xerosis in 8-12%; less frequently, they may induce cutaneous lupus erythematosus and vitiligo-like lesions (5). Serious reactions have included cases of toxic epidermal necrolysis, Stevens-Johnson syndrome, and acute generalized exanthematous pustulosis (5).

The reported cases of ribociclib-induced vitiligo-like lesions show a variety of depigmentation degrees (5,8). Some cases describe localized lesions, while others report extensive depigmentation affecting large body areas (2,10). Most affected patients continued ribociclib therapy without requiring specific treatment for the lesions (9). However, most case series indicated topical corticosteroids and calcineurin inhibitors as first-line treatment, with little or no response (10,11).

Some reports indicate partial or complete repigmentation after discontinuing ribociclib, while others describe persistent depigmentation despite cessation of therapy (5,6). To date, there is no consensus regarding the treatment of these lesions (3). The therapeutic objective is based on preventing cancer progression with an adequate response to oncological treatment, but not focusing on the repigmentation of the lesions (3).

Clinicians should be aware of this dermatologic toxicity to provide proper counseling and management strategies (5). While vitiligo-like lesions are not a contraindication for continued ribociclib therapy, their recognition is essential to differentiate them from other cutaneous adverse events requiring intervention (9,11). Further studies are needed to understand the long-term outcomes of these lesions and their impact on patient quality of life.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

Vitiligo-like is a side effect associated with ribociclib. The pathogenesis is likely immune-mediated, and some lesions persist despite discontinuation, others may improve with or without treatment. Considering the social stigma associated with vitiligo, it is important to be aware of this adverse effect and counsel the patients before starting the therapy. More research is needed to elucidate risk factors, incidence, and potential therapeutic interventions for ribociclib-induced dermatologic toxicities.

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